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- Solar and Hybrid Thermal Systems
- Solar Photovoltaic Systems
- Shallow Geothermal Energy Applications
- Storages with Phase Change Materials (PCM)
- Energy Efficiency
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- Hydrogen Energy

ALTERNATIVE MATERIALS

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Evaporation Temperature	77.6 °C
Turbine Inlet Temperature	97.5°C
Condensing Temperature	18.6 °C
Turbine Isentropic efficiency	0.85
Pump Isentropic efficiency	0.8

Fig.2. Exergy losses diagram (Given as the percent ages of the total exergy destruction)

Fig.3. Impact of geothermal fluid mass flow rate on turbine work (kW)

As it can be seen in Fig.3, an increase in mass flow rate of the geo fluid leads a significant increase in turbine work. As a result, re-injection process should be kept maintaining carefully for the sustainability of the geothermal source and for supplying sufficient amount of geothermal fluid to the plant in long-term. In Fig.4, impact of the geothermal well head temperature variation on the turbine work is presented. It was seen that, power output of the turbine increases as the resource temperature increases. As a result, it is important to consider cooling predictions associated with re-injection process. Sending geo fluid at very low temperatures to the re-injection well is not recommended and the temperature of the re-injection fluid should be controlled carefully. As shown in Fig.5, the increase in the evaporation temperature results in an increase of the both energy and exergy efficiency of the system. When the evaporator temperature varies from 60 to 100°C, energy efficiency of the plant changes from 0.088 to 0.1368, exergy efficiency increases from 0.2858 to 0.4242 and turbine work output

increases from 2143 kW to 3323 kW, respectively.

Fig.4 Impact of geothermal fluid well head on turbine work (kW)

Fig. 5 Impact of evaporation temperature on energy (η_{cycle}) and exergy efficiency (η_{ex}) of the plant

Fig.6. Impact of condensation temperature on energy (η_{cycle}) and exergy efficiency (η_{ex}) of the plant

As shown in Fig.6 as the condenser temperature increases, energy and exergy efficiency of the plant decreases. When the condenser temperature varies from 15 to 30°C, energy efficiency of the plant decreases from 0.1201 to 0.093, exergy efficiency of the plant decreases from 0.3843 to 0.2789, respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, energy, exergy analysis and thermodynamic modelling of a geothermal ORC power plant is presented. These analyses are expected to be a useful reference for the designers and researchers who are interested in geothermal based ORC power plants.

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Optimization methodology of borehole heat exchangers (BHE) according geometric characteristics, material properties and installation and operating cost

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One of the biggest challenges for the geothermal heat pump market is the high cost associated with drilling of borehole heat exchangers. Achieving more thermal efficient geothermal heat exchangers would reduce this cost, as a shorter length of heat exchanger would be necessary to obtain the same operating temperatures (same efficiency of the heat pump).

Keywords: Shallow geothermal energy, borehole heat exchangers, new materials, Plastic Pipes, Grouting Material, Increased Efficiency, Cost Saving, multi-criteria analysis

INTRODUCTION

The thermal efficiency of a borehole heat exchanger is characterised by its thermal resistance. This parameter originally comes from the works of [1] and [2] where the thermal behaviour of geothermal heat exchangers is modelled on the basis of the following key parameters:

- (i) the conductivity of the ground,
- (ii) the thermal resistance of the borehole heat exchanger,
- (iii) the undisturbed ground temperature and,
- (iv) the injection (or extraction) of heat ratio (thermal power input).

Therefore, the thermal efficiency of a borehole heat exchanger is determined by its thermal resistance. This parameter is modelled from the following key parameters:

- Properties and flow of the fluid through the heat exchanger,
- Diameter of the geothermal borehole,
- Geometry and materials of the heat exchanger pipe, and,
- Grouting material.

The higher the thermal resistance of the heat exchanger, the lower the heat transferred between the heat carrier fluid and the ground, resulting in a greater need for buried heat exchanger length. This parameter should consequently be optimised as minimally as possible.

BACKGROUND

Based on the thermal transfer model in a geothermal borehole exchanger [1], there are numerous publications on the resistance of a

geothermal borehole. Some studies have used finite element numerical techniques, but rigorous, they have also proven cumbersome to use.

Others have proposed analytical solutions [3] [4] that are easily applied but can only be applied to a limited type of pipe geometries, under certain conditions. These studies showed that increased thermal conductivity of grouting and the placement of piping close to the wall of the geothermal borehole improve the thermal performance, and [5] subsequently demonstrated this fact in experimental field thermal tests. A finite element model has also been published for the case of a two-loop (double U) probe in a geothermal borehole [6], following the work of [7]. Finally, there is also a comparative study of helicoidal and triple U probes in foundation piles [8].

In spite of the described antecedents, no studies have been found that analyse in a global way the impact of each one of the parameters that influence in the final result of the thermal resistance of the geothermal heat exchanger including a multi-objective analysis that also considers economic restrictions and costs, both in execution (CAPEX) and exploitation (OPEX).

METHODOLOGY

Based on the different analytical expressions that model the thermal resistance of the geothermal heat exchanger, a multi-criteria analysis will be carried out in order to obtain the optimum values of the different parameters. To this end, analytical models will be compiled describing the influence of the factors on the thermal transfer of the heat exchanger with the ground, obtaining the

relationship of the thermal resistance and, therefore, of its thermal efficiency. With all these expressions, the different criteria to be considered will be defined (maximising the thermal efficiency of the exchanger (i.e. minimising the thermal resistance value of the exchanger) and minimising the total cost associated with the exchanger).

In the case of the total costs associated with the geothermal heat exchanger, the installation costs of the borehole will be analysed (drilling, geothermal probe, grouting, ..) and the operating costs (the electricity consumption of the heat pump during its operating time and the electricity consumption of the circulation pump necessary to overcome hydraulic losses, which will require a hydraulic study of the installation).

On the other hand, experimental thermal tests will also be carried out to validate the conclusions obtained from the analytical study described above. In order to achieve this objective, a series of thermal tests (called Thermal Response Test, or TRT) will be carried out with a constant and controlled thermal power injection that will allow the thermal transfer in the borehole to be evaluated and, therefore, the main thermal characteristics of the heat exchanger to be extracted, thus enabling its thermal behaviour to be evaluated (for example, the thermal study evaluated at a foundation pile used as a borehole heat exchanger [8]).

The methodology to be used in these tests is described in [9] and highlights the importance of thermal heat injection control (by means of a Proportional Integral Derivative controller, PID) and evaluating it at the borehole, since in this way more precise results are obtained than in the traditional methodology, where no control of thermal injection is carried out, limiting itself to the generation of a constant heat pulse that does not take into account, for example, the thermal losses of the pipes or the thermal influence of the external temperature.

Therefore, verification of analytical optimisation results by means of experimental thermal tests will allow firm, coherent and robust conclusions to be drawn.

CONCLUSIONS

The obtained results will then be confronted with experimental thermal tests to validate the thermal efficiency of the borehole with the new developed products and configurations through the development of a state-of-the-art geothermal laboratory that provides controlled and detailed

heat injection, gathering in detail the variables involved in the heat exchange process of the borehole heat exchanger.

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Optimization of geothermal piles for ten-story building

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The article presents the optimization of geothermal pile for ten-story building. An optimization model OPTPILE was used, in order to obtain optimal design of geothermal pile. The model contains the cost objective function, geotechnical and structural design constraints. For a 10-story building with different spacing of piles, the optimal design of geothermal pile was obtained. The applied loads on the geothermal pile were calculated by using the 3D concrete building model. The optimal design for geothermal pile and the spacing of piles for 10-story building is obtained. The cost of installation of heating pipes in the pile represent 8% of total construction costs of pile foundation.

Keywords: Energy, Pile foundation, Modelling, optimization.

INTRODUCTION

The design of geothermal piles presented in few studies and research papers [1-3]. Also some experimental and numerical investigations of the behaviour of a heat exchanger pile were performed [4, 5]. The Ground Source Heat Pump Association (GSHP) [6] provide a design chart for additional settlement of pile heads in clay, due to thermal effects. In this paper the design of energy pile was obtained optimization procedure. Based on soil stratification, field test the crucial soils parameters were estimated. The energy foundation piles supports a ten-story concrete building. Four different spacing of piles were considered in this paper. Smaller spacing of piles results in smaller load applied on pile, however than a larger number of piles is needed. Fewer piles are needed if the spacing of piles is increased, but the large load is then applied on pile. A mixed-integer nonlinear programming (MINLP) optimization model OPTPILE (OPTimal PILE) developed by Jelusic and Žlender [7, 8] was used to solve the optimization problem. The model includes an objective function of the building material and labor costs. The objective function was limited by geotechnical and structural constraints in order to satisfy the requirements of Eurocode [9] specifications and GSHP recommendations [6].

The aim of the optimization was to obtain minimum self-manufacturing costs of the pile and optimal design variables such as: the diameter of the pile, the pile length, the diameter and number of main reinforcement bars and the diameter and

spacing of the links. Five different conditions were considered in optimization model OPTPILE: Condition 1 - the pile design resistance, Condition 2 - the settlement of the pile, Condition 3 - the required main steel reinforcement area must not exceed the provided steel reinforcement area in the pile, Condition 4 - the minimum area of the main reinforcement must be provided and Condition 5 - the minimum area of shear reinforcement (links) must be provided. While the repeated cycling of the thermal effects results in a degradation of the shaft friction along the pile the accumulation of settlement of pile was observed. This additional settlement caused by repeated cycling of the thermal effects was taken into design conditions for geothermal pile.

Fig.1. Ten-story concrete building, piles spacing 9 m.